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**Effects of Guidance and Counseling on
the Academic Performance of Secondary
School Students in Kaltungo Local
Government Area, Gombe State, Nigeria**

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Abstract

The purpose of education is not only to impart knowledge but also to develop the whole person. Students need more than academic excellence to succeed in life; they also require social, emotional, and behavioral skills. Guidance and counseling services in schools play a vital role in ensuring that students receive a holistic education that prepares them for the challenges of life. The objectives of this paper are to: 1) To explore the role of guidance and counseling in enhancing students' academic and personal growth in secondary school of Kaltungo LGA. 2) To assess the effects of guidance and counseling on the academic performance of secondary school students in Kaltungo LGA. 3) To investigate the relationship between guidance and counseling and students' discipline in secondary schools in Kaltungo LGA. This study adopted an ex-post facto research design. It targeted population was 2000 students and teachers. A random sample of 200 students, ten teacher counselors and ten head teachers were selected from the ten selected schools. Data were collected through the administration of questionnaires on the selected respondents. The collected data was then processed and analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics with the aid of mean and standard deviation. The study found that guidance and

counseling services in schools help to identify and address the social, emotional, and behavioral needs of students, thus improving their academic performance. Counseling services also help students to develop personal and social skills that are essential for their success in school and beyond. The integration of guidance and counseling services in schools can help to create a conducive learning environment, promote student well-being and enhance academic achievement. Guidance and counseling services are crucial in ensuring that schools provide a holistic education that goes beyond academic excellence. The integration of guidance and counseling services in schools can help to create a conducive learning environment, promote student well-being and enhance academic achievement. Teachers and counselors need to work together to ensure that students receive the support they need to succeed in school and beyond. The following were the recommendations made. The principals in secondary schools should put in place guidance and counseling services and provide an office where privacy is made a priority. This will encourage more students to visit the office. Guidance and counseling teachers should be well trained on how to carry out their duties. To have adequate provision of guidance and counseling materials as well as application of peer counseling, there is need to make proper budgeting for the same in terms of finances and time respectively. Guest speakers should be invited to provide the counseling services to the students in areas of concern.

Keywords: Guidance, Counseling, Academic Performance, Secondary school, Education

Introduction

Guidance and counseling are two closely interrelated concepts, and each determines the availability and effectiveness of the other. According to Okita and Odiambo (2016), “guidance” refers to an abroad area of all educational activities and services aimed at assisting individual students to understand themselves and adjust to school life. Oye, Obi, Mohd and Bernice (2019), define “counseling” as an interpersonal relationship in which one person attempts to help another person to understand and cope with problems emanating from education, vocation and family relationship. Guidance and counseling is therefore aimed at bringing about maximum development and self-realization of human potential for the benefit of the individual and the society. Oniye and Alawane (2016), opined that guidance and counseling programme assists the student in harmonizing their abilities, interest, values and enable them to develop their full potential. It direct student on appropriate career and subject choices; solving discipline, education, social and psychological problems; and general adjustment to

school life. Anaeto, B., and Ajibo, B. C. (2023), guidance is interpreted as a specialized service to help the individual to solve certain major problems—personal, educational, and vocation. He further opined that guidance involves personal assistance which is given by an expert to an individual which is designed to assist the him or her to decide where he wants to go, what he wants to do and how best to accomplish his/her purpose. The development of guidance and counseling originated in Europe and the United States of America in 1900’s. In 1911, Meyer Bloomfield organized a wide guidance programme in the USA that catered for students. The emphasis was on vocational information, awareness of the world of work, the location of employment and reduction of examination anxiety (Dabone, K., at el, 2015). They noted that since the 1950’s, opinion about guidance and counseling have changed rapidly and that understanding youth’s problems are among the functions of school guidance and counseling. To buttress this assertion, a study with a random sample of 100 counselor education programmes which evaluates the effect of counseling on students was carried out in the USA. The study found out that guidance and counseling significantly influence academic performance of a student. This is an indication that most institutions have put emphasis on the need for academic excellence and more so the intervention through guidance and counseling programmes. This development made teacher counselors to provide guidance and counseling services at secondary schools, not only to students who are underachieving, maladjusted but also to gifted children who do not know what to do with their abilities. Omoniyi (2016) state that it is generally accepted that in Nigeria the organized and formal guidance and counseling service started in 1959 at St. Theresa’s College, Oke-Ado Ibadan, by a group of dedicated religious reverend sisters who had the perception of the need for proper guidance in job selection for their secondary school leavers. They invited some twenty outsiders to advise them about placing sixty of their final year female students in appropriate careers. This is about eight decades after the birth of an established and functional guidance and counseling services in America.

The Federal Ministry of Education in its efforts to encourage guidance education established a guidance counseling unit in 1961 to be supervised by an education officer in the ministry. This was temporarily suspended in 1966 as a result of the civil war but re-visited in at the onset of the 6-3-3-4 system of education. By the end of the 70s, the government had already

recognized the importance of guidance and counseling in the educational, economic and social life of the nation. In the 3rd national development plan (1975-1980) emphasis was geared towards achieving the manpower needs of the nation. The government then realized that for education to be complete, the beneficiary must have a good sense of fulfillment. This led to the inauguration of the Counseling Association of Nigeria in 1976 as an affiliation of the American Personnel and Guidance Association (APGA). The Federal Government then inserted the need for guidance and counseling services and courses in our schools in its National Policy on Education by 1981. This then led the state governors to establish guidance and counseling units in their ministries of education, in addition to counseling units that are available in the universities. It is statutorily observed that the academic performance of secondary schools in Kaltungo local government area has been declining over. This has a negative reflection on the various programmes put in place to promote academic performance in the area by the education ministry of the state. The main concern of the study, therefore, was to investigate the role of guidance and counseling programme in improving the students and facilitating better achievement in academic performance. This study sought to provide some insights into these issues and establish the relationship between guidance and counseling and academic performance of secondary school student in Kaltungo local government area.

Statement of the Problem

In this 21st century, young people are living in an exciting time with an increasingly diverse and mobile society with new technologies and expanding opportunities. Adolescents face unique and diverse challenges both personally and developmentally that has affected their academic performance. In schools, success is measured by the level of the students' academic performance because students' performance remains a top priority for teachers but it is unfortunate to know that the academic performance of secondary school students has been declining over time most especially in Kaltungo LGA. The goal of education cannot be achieved without the input of professional counselors. Counseling programs play a vital role in preventing educational, personal, social, mental and emotional problems. Many school administrators in Kaltungo LGA of Gombe state are yet to embrace the program because they do not see the benefit of appropriate

counseling services. Many of them prefer to use their teachers rather than professional counselors for guidance services. The new and advanced professional academic problem-solving techniques can only be delivered by qualified professionals. In schools where guidance and counseling services are available, the number of students attending counseling sessions is low and this has caused serious decline to the academic performance of secondary school students. Owing to the gap identified above, this study seeks to determine the influence of guidance and counseling on the academic performance of secondary school students in the Kaltungo local government area of Gombe state.

Research Objectives

1. To explore the role of guidance and counseling in enhancing students' academic and personal growth in secondary school of Kaltungo LGA.
2. To assess the effects of guidance and counseling on the academic performance of secondary school students in Kaltungo LGA.
3. To investigate the relationship between guidance and counseling and students' discipline in secondary schools in Kaltungo LGA.

Research Questions

1. How can we explore the role of guidance and counseling in enhancing students' academic and personal growth among students in secondary schools in Kaltungo LGA?
2. What are the effects of guidance and counseling on the academic performance of secondary school students in secondary schools in Kaltungo LGA?
3. What is the relationship between guidance and counseling and students' discipline in secondary schools in secondary schools in Kaltungo LGA?

Hypotheses

1. Null Hypotheses:

H₀: Utilization of guidance and counseling services do not significantly impact students' academic performance in secondary schools in Kaltungo LGA.

2. Null Hypothesis:

H₀: Utilization of guidance and counseling services do not significantly impact students' discipline in secondary schools in Kaltungo LGA.

Literature Review

Concept of Guidance

Literally guidance means to direct, to point out, to show the path. It is the assistance or help rendered by a more experienced person to a less experienced person to solve certain major problems of the individual (less experienced) i.e., educational, vocational, personal etc. Guidance is a concept as well as a process. As a concept guidance is concerned with the optimal development of the individual. As a process guidance helps the individual in self-understanding (understanding one's strengths, limitations, and other resources) and in self-direction (ability to solve problems, make choices and decision on one's own).

UNESCO (2020) define it as a process that helps individuals to develop self-awareness, self-direction, and decision-making skills. Omeje and Eze (2021), define guidance as an assistance made available by a competent counselor to an individual of any age to help them direct their own life, develop their own point of view, make their own decisions, and carry their own burdens. Adegoke (2018), emphasized the importance of guidance services in schools to help students gain knowledge and insight into the skills, attitudes, and values necessary to thrive in a constantly changing society. Egbo (2020), describes guidance as a set of services aimed at empowering individuals to navigate their circumstances effectively and become valuable members of both their community and themselves. Through guidance, clients can make decisions that promote self-direction and adaptation, enabling them to make meaningful adjustments to their environment, improve their educational pursuits, and set realistic goals. Egbo (2020) further highlights that guidance and counseling are geared towards enhancing clients' holistic development across various aspects of their lives, such as mental, vocational, emotional, intellectual, and socio- personal dimensions while emphasizing the importance of individual worth and dignity.

According to Jones (1970), the purpose of guidance has been “to assist the individual through counseling and to make wise choices, adjustment, and interpretations in connection with critical situation in his life in such a way as to insure continual growth in ability for self direction,” The Educational

Policies Commission (2018), views guidance as the keystone of the School programme. Guidance is also described as a “counseling service to assist the individual in achieving self direction and educational, vocational and personal adjustment and to take positive steps in the light of new orientations” (Rogers, 2018).

Concept of Counseling

According to Gustad (1953)," Counseling is a learning oriented process, carried on a simple, one-to-one social environment, in which the counselor, professionally competent in relevant psychological skills and knowledge, seeks to assist the client, by methods appropriate to the latter's needs and within the context of the total personal program, to learn how to put such understanding into effect in relation to more clearly perceived, realistically defined goals to the end that the client may become a happier and more productive member of society ".

According to Patterson (2021)," Counseling is the process involving interpersonal relationship between a therapist and one or more clients by which the former employs psychological methods based on systematic knowledge of the human personality in attempting to improve the mental health of the latter ".

Counseling plays a vital role in a comprehensive guidance system, enabling clients to achieve their goals by making informed decisions and finding solutions to interpersonal or emotional challenges. Clients also gain a better understanding of their perspectives on life through counseling, as highlighted by Ede and Nwagu (2021), who believe in every individual's potential for personal growth and self-realization.

Modo and Inaja (2017), define a counselor as someone with specialized training in counseling, available to support clients or students seeking guidance. Oyeleke et al (2022), perceives the counselor as a facilitator, responsible for nurturing the client's growth into a productive member of society and themselves, overseeing their educational, professional, and personal-social progress. To effectively manage their clients, counselors utilize a range of professional skills such as listening, responding, empathizing, questioning, interpreting, summarizing, and providing support, ensuring a personalized and plagiarism-free approach (Okobiah 2018).

The Concept of Guidance and Counseling

Guidance and counseling according to Birichi and Rukunga (2018), is a practice that had been in existence for a long time and had been passed on from one generation to another. The concept of guidance and counseling carry different but overlapping meaning. They are closely interrelated and cannot be overly separated from one another. Furthermore, Mutie and Ndambuki (2020), observed that, the belief that human beings are basically self-determining creatures. That means that they had an innate desire for independence and autonomy as well as for self-destruction which implied that human beings had the ability, to control their own destiny and to be fully responsible for their action. Main goal of guidance and counseling is to help people understand themselves in order to deal with life experiences in a healthy manner, by being able to recognize the factors that cause problems and look for appropriate methods of resolving or avoiding the situations that may lead to unhealthy lifestyles. Guidance and Counseling service, Ajowi and Simatwa (2020) noted that, they are essential elements in discipline management of people in all societies.

Guidance and counseling is a service that all human beings need at one point of their life. There is no human being that has never got a problem at one point or another. Once a problem arises, one seeks solutions, suggestions or even other people's opinions about the problem. In one way or another, one seeks for guidance and counseling services (Alutu, 2017; Garner, 2018). Guidance and counseling services are services that have been in existence as long as human beings have lived, either formally or informally. Guidance and counseling has been engraved in African traditional society since time immemorial. According to Busari (2020) and Muraina (2022) guidance and counseling was entrusted to the immediate and extended family where individuals confined in and depended upon their relatives for advice when faced with problems. As such in the African traditional society, people of all ages could seek for this service from the elderly or respected people in the society such as fortune-tellers, wizards, astrologers, palmists and future-tellers were thought to be getting information from the gods and could therefore guide and counsel others according to what the gods have counseled.

Types of Guidance and Counseling Service Rendered in Secondary Schools

The types of guidance and counseling service mainly practiced in the school setting are:

1. ***Educational guidance and counseling:*** This involves activities such as assisting students with problems of learning, teaching and of education generally. It assists students to develop to their maximum potentials and to function effectively in their school programme.
2. ***Vocational guidance and counseling:*** This is an aspect of counseling to ensure that child is assisted in making right and realistic choice of career. It looks into problems of selection of training for and adjustment to occupation.
3. ***Personal and psychological guidance and counseling:*** This deals with personal problems and problems of overall life's adjustment. The counselor assists student to resolve such problems in individuals or group sessions or refer the student to the appropriate channel when the problems are beyond his competence.
4. ***Individual guidance and counseling:*** This deals with problems or stressful feelings which occur in the life of everyone. It offers an opportunity to the students to experience a one-to-one relationship which makes the students have enough understanding of themselves so as to be able to stand on their own feet without support.
5. ***Group guidance and counseling:*** It helps students to freely discuss their problems in the presences of group member with the same problem. The discussion viewed at attracting solution to the problems. It helps the counselor to cope with their day-to-day adjustment and developmental problems because of its focus on the experiences and feelings of its members.

Education Functions of Guidance at the Secondary Schools

- i. ***Helping the students to orient to the school situation:*** Helping the students to orient to the school situation and aiding them to make a good beginning from the secluded life of the home. The student enters the vast area of the school and its environment and the adjustment required is tremendous. The educational guidance programme emphasizes the purpose of complete education, preventing dropouts and utilizing the available human resources.

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- ii. ***Helping the students to learn effectively:*** A well thought-out guidance programme will cater to the individual difference in students and detect the learning difficulties mainly in terms of reading, writing and comprehension and provide remedial programme through diagnostic devices. The level of achievement is hampered by these specific difficulties unless they are identified first and continuous effort is made to rectify them.
 - iii. ***Helping students to develop desirable attitude:*** Desirable attitudes are the cornerstone for developing well balanced personality. The students' interest in the school and his motivation for continuous hard work, depends to a great extent on the attitudes he has developed. Healthy and positive attitudes towards self, teachers, classmates, the school and the community are essential for a happy and well-integrated life.
 - iv. ***Helping students to plan their immediate future:*** Students are very often unaware of the need for planning. Even in their early years, the students can be introduced into a system of wise planning beginning with their daily activities.
 - v. ***Helping parents to co-operate with the school:*** Parents must have a knowledge of their children's activities in the school and keep a close contact with teacher in following the development of their children. Parent teacher meeting, parents' visits to the school to observe the school programmes and parent teacher child conferences are a must if there is to be an all-round development of the child in the home and in the school.
 - vi. ***Helping the students to have orientation to jobs:*** During the Secondary school level, students can be given opportunities to find out their aptitude and interest in occupations, jobs, by involving them in work experiences, socially useful and productive work and community and social-service activities. In this way beginning can be made in the selection of orientation to jobs/careers.

The Roles of Counselor to the Students

The school counselor assists students in various ways such as:

1. The counselor helps the students to develop self-awareness such as knowing their actual value, interest, capacities, attitude, strength and weaknesses.

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2. He helps them to understand their environment and the resources within the school such as library, laboratory facilities, sports field and games available, club, administrative facilities among others.
 3. The counselor helps the student with several adjustment programme within and outside the school e.g., adjustment related to academic work, study habit, attitudes toward peers, teacher and adjustment to opposite sex.
 4. The counselor provides student with information covering nature and types of jobs available, duties involved, tools used, working condition, economic and advancement opportunities and job requirement.
 5. The counselor provides pupils/student with information for further studies including types of institute method of application and entry requirements.
 6. The counselor refers students to the appropriate remedial classes to improve their academic performances.
 7. The counselor assists the emotionally disturbed student to understand themselves better and find satisfactory solution to their emotional problems.
 8. The counselor helps in the orientation of new students and acts as guest speaker to schools on guidance issues.

How Guidance and Counseling Affects Secondary School Students' Academic Performance

Guidance and counseling services have a significantly positive effects on the academic performance of secondary school students by improving study habits, enhancing emotional well-being, and guiding career choices. These services reduce student anxiety, decrease disciplinary issues, and foster better time management, allowing students to focus on learning and achieve higher academic standards.

Key effects of guidance and counseling on academic performance include:

- i. **Enhanced Academic Skills:** Students learn effective study techniques, time management, and goal-setting strategies, which directly improve academic outcomes.
- ii. **Improved Behavior and Discipline:** Counseling helps reduce bullying and other disruptive behaviors, fostering a safer, more conducive, and positive environment for learning.

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- iii. ***Personal and Social Development:*** It addresses emotional, social, and psychological issues—such as stress and peer pressure which can otherwise hinder a student's ability to focus on academics.
 - iv. ***Educational and Career Direction:*** By helping students understand their aptitudes and interests, counselors guide them in selecting appropriate subjects and career paths, increasing motivation and academic persistence.
 - v. ***Increased Academic Performance:*** Studies indicate that students who receive counseling services show better academic results compared to those who do not, as they are better equipped to handle academic challenges.

However, the effectiveness of these services can be hindered by inadequate resources, lack of specific time allocation, and a shortage of trained personnel in schools.

Relationship between Guidance and Counseling

Guidance and counseling act as a crucial, proactive tool for managing and improving student discipline in secondary schools by addressing root causes of behavioral issues rather than just punishing them. It fosters self-discipline, responsibility, and positive behavioral choices through mentorship, counseling, and conflict resolution, directly reducing, and even replacing, reliance on traditional punitive measures.

Key aspects of the relationship:

- i. ***Preventative Approach:*** Instead of solely punishing, G&C prevents indiscipline by helping students navigate social, emotional, and psychological pressures, which are often the root causes of misbehavior.
- ii. ***Behavioral Modification:*** Counselors use techniques like workshops and one-on-one sessions to help students change negative behaviors, promoting responsibility and self-discipline.
- iii. ***Supportive Intervention:*** When discipline issues arise, guidance services offer a, constructive intervention that addresses the student's underlying problems, leading to long-term behavioral change.
- iv. ***Conflict Resolution:*** Counselors teach students skills to manage stress, anxiety, and conflicts, which reduces instances of violence or disruption in school.

- v. *Positive School Culture:* Effective G&C services foster a supportive environment where students feel heard and understood, which reduces the likelihood of defiance.

Studies shows a significant positive relationship between active guidance services and improved student discipline. Enhanced counseling units, trained counselors, and strong peer counseling programs directly correlate with reduced, and better managed, student misbehavior.

1. The main goal of guidance and counseling is to give an opportunity to a person to see a variety of available options as to assist or help the person in making wise choices.
2. Guidance and counseling both aimed at assisting students to draw up their own plans of academic and non-academic pursuits and arrived at right decisions and find solutions to his problems.
3. It is not specific to any stages of development of a student in educational institutions, student's physical and mental health and his adjustment issues at home, school vocational and social demands, relationships etc. guidance and counseling emphasis on all these areas.
4. It is a continuous process extending all throughout one's life. There is nothing like a one shot and for one time guidance and counseling. It is a continuous process.

Theoretical Framework

This study was based on the principles of person-centered and social learning theory. The person-centered theory emphasizes on the human interaction between two people (the counselor and the client, in this case). Social learning theory, on the other hand, postulates that a child learns behavior through social interaction in the form of observation and imitation of what other people in the society are doing.

Person-Centered Theory

This theory focuses on the human interaction between the counselor and the client. Rogers (1980) called it the Person-centered theory in order to suggest that his principles extended beyond the client-therapist relationship to encompass all human interaction. The current person-centered theory is understood as a process of helping clients discover new and more satisfying personal meanings about themselves and the world they inhabit.

The student will drive towards growth, health and adjustment (Makinde, 2019). The model assumes that human interaction is only possible when certain conditions prevail. In the case of guidance and counseling, these conditions should prevail counselor's demonstration in the counselor-client orientation. According to Omoniyi (2016), these conditions include counselor's demonstration of empathy, unconditional positive regard and warmth to the client. He notes that growth occurs in an acceptance, warm, empathetic, non-judgmental environment that allows students the freedom to explore their thoughts and feelings and to solve their own problems. Guidance and counseling programme that lacks these characteristics culminate into poor performance of students in school. When a counselor communicates the above conditions, those being helped will become less defensive and more open to themselves and their world and they will behave in more social and constructive ways. Many students harbour feelings of failure in academics and thus have low self-esteem, but a counselor is able to counter the feelings by working towards fostering the student's capacity to hope and believe that they are capable of overcoming academic failure they are experiencing and even end up performing their best potentialities. A conducive environment for the student should be provided and teachers should provide room for self-actualization by being friendly, loving, competent and responsible (Tambuwal, 2016). Teacher counselor should also help the student set goals and allow positive self-recognition after attaining set goals and aspirations that will boost success in academic performance. Therefore, a good environment should be created by teacher counselor.

Social Learning Theory

Learning is a process where behaviors are learnt or acquired from the environment. One way of learning is through social observation and imitation. This theory is advanced by Albert Bandura (1986). This theory explains delinquency as a behavior learnt through the complex process of socialization. The theory postulates that the behavior is reflective of people observing and imitating others and imagining the consequence of their own behavior. The theory advocates that human behavior is modified using learning principles to change behavior (Omoniyi, 2018).

The behavioral approach emphasizes that the client defines goals in behavioral terms provide resources and encouragement in helping clients

more towards goals and helps clients with different problems (Patterson, 2020). Teacher counselors can therefore apply this in counseling students concerning their academic performance. Makinde (2019) notes that counseling effectiveness and outcome of counseling are assessed by change in the specific student's behavior. This implies that counseling can use behavioral counseling to create a conducive environment for the students to modify their behaviors in order to solve their academic problems through creation of learning conditions. Teacher counselors can use behavioral techniques like self-management programmers and self-directed behaviors which may deal with learning, study and time management skills in schools. This will foster the students' academic performance. The student will drive towards growth, health and adjustment (Makinde, 2019). Therefore, a good environment created by the teacher counselor. School can provide room for good self-concept that will boost success in academic performance. All the two theories focus on developing trust between the counselee and the students making the students to open up their challenges in other to get solution.

Research Methodology

In conducting this research, a questionnaire has been designed to help the researchers acquire the needed information. The survey research design through the administration of questionnaires was used for the study. In this study, questionnaire serves as useful guide to the effort of generating data for this study.. The population under study comprised 2000 students and teachers from various schools in Kaltungo LGA of Gombe state. This diverse cohort of participants encompassed a range of socioeconomic backgrounds and school locations, ensuring that the research findings were holistic and reflective of the broader community. To ensure the representativeness of the sample, a stratified random sampling technique was utilized. This method involved dividing the population into distinct strata based on specific characteristics, socioeconomic status and location of the schools, followed by the random selection of participants from each stratum. This methodological approach facilitated the adequate representation of all segments within the population. The determination of the sample size for this study was conducted through statistical calculations, considering factors like the desired level of confidence and margin of error. By incorporating statistical methodologies in determining the sample size, the researchers guaranteed

the reliability and validity of the study's outcomes. This rigorous methodological framework served to mitigate bias and enhance the overall quality of the research. The data collection process involved distribution of the questionnaire to respondents after explaining the goal of the study to them.

The methodology employed in the study involved data collection through the utilization of a questionnaire featuring a four-point Likert scale that encompasses categories of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D), and Strongly Disagree (SD). These categories were assigned numerical values of 4, 3, 2, and 1 respectively. Their purpose was to gather insights regarding the perceptions of students and teachers concerning the influence of guidance and counseling on academic performance among secondary school students in Kaltungo LGA.

Results and Discussion

Research Question 1. What are the effects of guidance and counseling on the academic performance of students?

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation results of respondents on the impact of guidance and counseling on academic performance of students.

S/N	Items	Mean	SD	Decisions
1	The guidance and counseling sessions have helped students improve in their study habits and time management skills.	3.44	1.29	Agreed
2	Guidance and counseling improve students' learning.	4.11	1.05	Agreed
3	Students feel more motivated to work hard and succeed academically after attending guidance and counseling sessions.	4.07	1.32	Agreed
4	The guidance and counseling sessions have helped students cope with stress and anxiety related to academic challenges.	3.30	1.44	Agreed
5	Students are more confident in their abilities and skills because of the guidance and counseling sessions they have attended.	4.51	0.82	Agreed

6	Students feel more focused and determined to achieve their academic goals after receiving guidance and counseling.	3.91	1.22	Agreed
7	Average Mean	3.89	1.19	Agreed
8	Cut-off mean	2.50		

Based on the results presented in Table 1, it is evident that guidance and counseling have positive effects on the academic performance of students. The mean scores for each item indicate that students generally agreed that the counseling sessions helped them improve study habits, time management skills (M=3.44 SD=1.29), improving students learning (M=4.11, SD= 1.05) motivation (M=4.07, SD=1.32), coping with stress (M=3.30 SD=1.44), boosting confidence (4.51, SD=0.82), and maintaining focus on academic goals (M=3.91, SD=1.22). The cut-off means of 2.50 also indicates that the impact of guidance and counseling is perceived to be significant.

Research Question 2. What is the relationship between guidance and counseling and students' discipline?

Table 2: Mean and standard deviation results of respondents on the impact of guidance and counseling on student's discipline.

S/N	Items	Mean	SD	Decisions
1	The guidance and counseling services at my school have effectively reduced instances of violence.	4.03	0.85	Agreed
2	The guidance and counseling services at my school have helped in preventing bullying among students.	4.01	1.08	Agreed
3	I believe that the guidance and counseling services at my school have positively influenced the image students have of themselves.	4.06	0.78	Agreed
4	The guidance and counseling services at my school have played a role in reducing truancy rates among students.	3.31	0.97	Agreed

5	I feel that the guidance and counseling services at my school have successfully reduced the number of student suspensions.	3.42	1.07	Agreed
6	The guidance and counseling services at my school have effectively addressed the root causes of student conflicts, leading to a decrease in fights.	3.40	1.01	Agreed
7	Average Mean	3.54	0.99	Agreed
8	Cut-off mean	2.50		

The results of the survey in Table 2 indicate that students perceive the guidance and counseling services at the schools is positive. The majority of students agreed that these services have been effective in reducing instances of violence ($M=4.03$, $SD=0.85$), preventing bullying ($M=4.01$, $SD=1.08$), improving self-image ($M=4.06$, $SD=0.78$), reducing truancy rates ($M=3.31$, $SD=0.97$), decreasing student suspensions ($M=3.42$, $SD=1.07$), and addressing root causes of conflicts ($M=3.40$, $SD=1.01$).

These results highlight the important role that guidance and counseling play in student discipline and well-being in secondary schools.

Hypothesis Testing

1. Null Hypothesis: What is the relationship between guidance and counseling and students' discipline in the school? The results of the survey in Table 2 indicate that students perceive the guidance and counseling services in the school is positive. The majority of students agreed that these services have been effective in reducing instances of violence in their school and even in the community ($M=4.03$, $SD=0.85$), preventing bullying ($M=4.01$, $SD=1.08$), improving self-image ($M=4.06$, $SD=0.78$), reducing truancy rates ($M=3.31$, $SD=0.97$), decreasing student suspensions ($M=3.42$, $SD=1.07$), H_0 : Utilization of guidance and counseling services do not significantly affect the students' academic performance.

Discussion

The findings of the study revealed that counseling plays a significant role that affects the performance of secondary school students in Kaltungo LGA. This aligns with the study by Oyeleke et al. (2022), who argued that counseling services in schools provide learners with the necessary support

to foster holistic development, particularly by addressing emotional and social challenges. Similarly, Uzonwanne and Okonkwo (2022) highlighted that effective counseling can lead to improved academic performance and social skills by assisting learners in overcoming personal and emotional barriers. The emotional and social development of learners, as found in this study, is crucial in shaping their overall well-being and academic success, in line with Nwachukwu et al. (2021), who emphasized that counseling is integral in nurturing emotional intelligence and moral growth, key components of holistic education. By enabling learners to critically engage with content and reflect on societal issues, these approaches promote not only academic growth but also the development of ethical and social values. Similarly, Adeoye and Nwangwu (2022) highlighted that emotional intelligence, when nurtured through counseling, enhances the effectiveness of transformative teaching methods by improving student-teacher relationships and fostering a supportive learning environment. The combined efforts of counseling and transformative teaching provide a holistic support system that addresses both the emotional and intellectual needs of learners, as further supported by Okeke and Udo (2023), who emphasized that this integration helps in creating a more inclusive educational environment, where learners are empowered to achieve their full potential. Hence, these findings underline the importance of counseling in creating a supportive educational environment that not only addresses the emotional needs of learners but also enhances their cognitive, social, and moral development. The integration of counseling with transformative teaching approaches offers a comprehensive approach to human development, preparing learners for success in both academic and social spheres.

Conclusion

Guidance and counseling programme have a positive impact on the academic performance of secondary school students, there is low academic performance by the majority of the students, students are aware of the role and importance of career counseling in their schools, stakeholders adequately support guidance and counseling programme in schools, guidance and counseling differs in rendered services among schools and teachers have low levels of training in guidance and counselling.

The study revealed that guidance and counseling has great impact on the academic performance of secondary school students. The respondents (students) all agreed that guidance and counseling helps them a lot in improving their reading habit and also helps them a lot in managing their time as can be seen from no significant difference in the mean responses of male and female students on the issues. Reading in the night, joining study groups, carrying out assignments, developing interest in subjects that are hated, making use of the school library during free periods, developing the habit of studying every evening after rest, minimizing the time spent on television and making use of personal time table are different ways guidance and counseling can help students in improving their reading habits and managing their time thereby, adjusting themselves and achieving better performance academically. In view of this research report, the employment of guidance counselors in every school appears to be imperative and urgent if our educational system is to be redeemed.

Guidance and counseling helps students make informed decisions about their lives and future ambitions. The role of a counselor in building the confidence of a student cannot be overstated, as it allows for a healthy relationship that promotes trust and the sharing of vital information. Furthermore, counseling is not only necessary for Children's/students in school environment but also for adults who may be facing difficult situations in their personal or professional lives. It is important to understand that seeking guidance and counseling is a sign of strength, and not a weakness. With the right guidance, individuals can overcome challenges and achieve their desired goals.

Additionally, guidance and counseling play a crucial role in promoting the mental and emotional well-being of children/students in schools. Counselors can help students identify and manage their emotions, cope with stress and anxiety, and build healthy relationships with their peers, teachers and family members. By providing a safe and non-judgmental space for students to express themselves, counselors can empower them to navigate the challenges of life and develop the resilience and coping skills necessary for a successful and fulfilling future. Overall, guidance and counseling are valuable tools in promoting the holistic development of students at school, family level and empowering them to become confident, responsible, and well-adjusted members of society.

Recommendations

The researcher recommends the following:

1. Schools should put in place guidance and counseling services and provide an office where privacy is made a priority. This will encourage more students to visit the office.
2. Guidance and counseling teachers should be well trained on how to carry out their duties by being sent to attend many seminars and workshops to improve on their skills.
3. For adequate provision of guidance and counseling materials as well as application of peer counseling, there ought to be proper budgeting for the same in terms of finances and time respectively.
4. There is need to invite guest speakers who will provide the counseling services to the students in areas of concern.
5. Student inventory, bulletins on different topics, handbooks for different educational opportunities, books on social psychology, psychology magazines should be provided to the school to improve the department.
6. The principals should employ professional counselors and discard the use of career masters in schools.
7. The school administrators should give necessary support to the counselor by creating awareness on the importance of guidance and counseling in the school.
8. The counselors should apply all the necessary skills and techniques in order to get the best out of the students who come to them for assistance.

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